

Tailored intervention improves statin adherence and reduces LDL-cholesterol levels

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Abstract

Background: Inadequate compliance with statin therapy considerably affects the achievement of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) objectives. Tailored interventions aim to address individual patient barriers to improve medication adherence.

Objective: The objective of this study was to assess the efficacy of a tailored intervention in improving statin adherence and reducing LDL-C levels in patients with atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD).

Methods: A prospective one-group study utilizing a pre-test and post-test design was conducted, involving 70 patients. The inclusion criteria were: 1) patients with baseline LDL-C values recorded prior to the intervention; 2) patients who had undergone 40 mg atorvastatin therapy for a minimum of three months without reaching LDL-C targets; and 3) non-adherent patients. Adherence was assessed using the Short Form of the Adherence to Refills and Medications Scale (ARMS-SF) questionnaire.

Results: After the intervention, adherence improved significantly from 0% to 90% ($p < 0.001$), accompanied by a significant reduction in mean LDL-C levels from 100.19 mg/dL to 87.29 mg/dL ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Tailored intervention significantly improved adherence and reduced LDL-C levels. This method can be recommended as an effective strategy to improve medication adherence prior to therapy intensification or polymorphism testing in patients on high-intensity statin therapy.

Keywords

tailored intervention, medication adherence, high-intensity statin, cardiovascular disease, LDL cholesterol

Introduction

According to Heron (2019), cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading global cause of death and dis-

ability. According to Riskesdas (2018), the most common form of cardiovascular disease in Indonesia is coronary heart disease. The formation of atherosclerotic plaques is facilitated by LDL-C and its oxidized form (Ference et

al. 2017). For patients at extremely high risk, the European Society of Cardiology recommends lowering LDL-C levels to less than 55 mg/dL (less than 1.4 mmol/L) and achieving a reduction of at least 50% from baseline levels (Mach et al. 2020). A key intervention is high-intensity statin therapy, which involves taking 40–80 mg of atorvastatin or 20–40 mg of rosuvastatin daily and can lower LDL-C levels by 50% or more (Mach et al. 2020). Research indicates that only a small percentage of patients taking high-intensity statins achieve their LDL-C targets, even though this potential exists (Ray et al. 2021; Catapano et al. 2022; Barrios et al. 2023). When high-intensity statins fail to produce the desired effect, this study assesses medication adherence before introducing ezetimibe and PCSK9 inhibitors to the treatment regimen.

Several barriers to achieving LDL-C targets include clinical inertia, medication non-adherence, and systemic health policy issues (Underberg et al. 2022). Statin adherence is lower in developing countries, including Indonesia (Vika et al. 2016; Li et al. 2023). Various factors hinder adherence, reducing patients' ability to follow treatment regimens. The World Health Organization classifies non-adherence into five dimensions: socioeconomic, healthcare system, medical condition, therapy-related, and patient-related factors. These are also often categorized as either intentional or unintentional (Xu et al. 2020). Although numerous interventions have been developed to improve medication adherence, most have achieved only moderate success (Barker-Collo et al. 2015; Hedegaard et al. 2015; Pfaeffli-Dale et al. 2015).

Tailored intervention has been proposed as an appropriate strategy to enhance medication adherence by addressing patient-specific barriers rather than relying on a single, generalized approach (Xu et al. 2020). A previous study conducted in Spain found that tailored interventions delivered by healthcare providers, particularly community pharmacists, improved adherence to statin therapy. This improvement was associated with a reduction in total cholesterol levels and a healthier lifestyle (Oñatibia-Astibia et al. 2019). Tailored interventions are more effective because they consider the individual barriers that cause non-adherence and offer solutions specific to each patient's needs. Other studies have shown that this method achieves greater success than standard health education in reducing pain among individuals with diabetes (Xu et al. 2020). Therefore, further research is needed to examine the impact of tailored interventions in Indonesia, where unique sociodemographic factors, patient characteristics, and beliefs may influence adherence differently than in other countries.

Materials and methods

Research design

We used a one-group, pre- and post-test design to evaluate how personalized interventions affected atorvastatin adherence, LDL-C levels, and goal achievement. The study

was conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Surabaya, East Java, from July to October 2024.

Participants

The study population included ASCVD patients who were non-adherent to 40 mg atorvastatin therapy. The inclusion criteria were: 1) patients with baseline LDL-C values recorded before the intervention; 2) patients who had received 40 mg atorvastatin therapy for at least the previous three months without achieving LDL-C targets; and 3) patients willing to provide informed consent. Those without a communication device and individuals with cognitive deficits were excluded from the research. The exclusion criteria were: 1) patient death during the study period; 2) modifications in atorvastatin dosage or the addition of another lipid-lowering agent during the study; and 3) transfer to another healthcare facility. A minimum sample size of 57 was required to attain 90% power for detecting a difference in group proportions of 28%. The alpha level was set at 5%.

Research procedure

The intervention was designed based on patient-specific barriers to medication adherence. Structured interviews were conducted with each patient to identify these barriers. The intervention addressed all identified barriers and included: 1) education through an animated video, booklet, and poster; 2) changing the timing of atorvastatin intake from night to morning; and 3) patient empowerment via a WhatsApp group. Demographic and clinical data were collected from medical records and patient interviews during outpatient clinic visits. Information included names, ages, genders, medical record numbers, phone numbers, addresses, weights, heights, smoking habits, marital status, education level, occupation, obesity status, diagnoses, comorbidities, and concurrent medications. These data were verified through patient consultation.

LDL-C levels were obtained from medical records or interviews and categorized as pre-intervention and post-intervention. Statin adherence was assessed using the ARMS-SF questionnaire, selected for its demonstrated validity and reliability in chronic disease populations, including among individuals with low literacy (Kripalani et al. 2009). The ARMS-SF evaluates both medication refill behavior and actual medication intake, allowing for more targeted intervention development. Patients with a total ARMS-SF score of 7 were classified as adherent, while scores > 7 indicated non-adherence (Barati et al. 2018). Patients were followed monthly for three months, with continuous communication maintained regarding upcoming appointments. Adherence and LDL-C levels were reassessed at the final follow-up.

Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed descriptively to summarize sociodemographic and patient characteristics, baseline LDL-C profiles, therapeutic LDL-C target attainment, and adherence levels. To evaluate the intervention's impact

on adherence and LDL-C target attainment, statistical analyses were employed, including McNemar's test. Using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, we checked if the tailored intervention's effect on LDL-C fluctuations was normal. For data that followed a normal distribution, we used a paired t-test; for data that did not, we used the Wilcoxon test. Using linear regression, we looked at how medication adherence correlated with changes in LDL-C.

Research approval

This research was approved with an ethical certificate No. 1022/KEPK/VI/2024. Participants were provided with detailed explanations about the research, including its objectives, methods, and potential benefits. Furthermore, written consent was obtained from all participants.

Results

Seventy people took part in this study. Table 1 provides a breakdown of the study population's demographics and clinical features. The majority of patients were male (71.43%), and their ages ranged from 41 to 64 (64.29%). A significant portion of the participants (45.71%) had completed a moderate level of education, while most

(67.14%) were unemployed. The primary comorbidities were hypertension (77.14%), diabetes mellitus (48.57%), heart failure (15.71%), and stroke (12.86%).

Table 2 shows the detailed results of the questionnaire. Adherence was assessed using the ARMS-SF questionnaire, comprising seven questions categorized into two indicators, namely medication refill adherence and medication intake adherence.

Prior to the intervention, the highest non-adherence rate in the medication intake indicator was observed in question 1, "How often do you miss scheduled appointments?" The mean score was 2.1, with the most frequent response being "some of the time" (72.86%), followed by "most of the time" (18.57%). After the intervention, the mean score dropped to 1.04, with the majority of responses being "none of the time" (95.71%).

For the medication refill indicator, the highest non-adherence rate before the intervention was observed in question 4, "How often do you forget to get prescriptions refilled?" The mean score was 1.34, with the most frequent response being "none of the time" (43.33%), followed by "some of the time" (34.29%). After the intervention, the mean score decreased to 1.01, with 100.00% of participants responding "none of the time."

Table 3 shows the adherence analysis for 70 patients following the tailored intervention. The total mean ARMS-SF score for intake adherence and refill adherence indicators was 9.12 at baseline, which decreased to 7.15 after the intervention. The McNemar test results demonstrated a substantial improvement in adherence following the intervention ($p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that tailored interventions can improve patient medication adherence.

Table 4 illustrates the alterations in LDL-C levels prior to and following the tailored intervention, indicating an average decrease of 12.90 mg/dL. A linear regression analysis was performed to examine the correlation between adherence levels and LDL-C reduction. The findings indicated statistical significance ($p < 0.001$), implying that adherent patients experienced more substantial reductions in LDL-C than non-adherent patients.

Table 5 shows the relationship between adherence and LDL-C reduction post-tailored intervention. A statistically significant association was observed ($p < 0.05$), indicating that improved adherence was associated with greater reductions in LDL-C levels.

Table 6 illustrates LDL-C target attainment prior to and following the tailored intervention. Before the intervention, all patients were categorized as non-adherent, with none achieving the target set by the 2019 European Society of Cardiology (ESC) guidelines. Following the intervention, 63 patients attained adherence, with two (2.86%) meeting the target stipulated in the 2019 ESC guidelines. Eight patients exhibited a reduction surpassing 50% from baseline LDL-C levels, while five achieved levels below 55 mg/dL. The McNemar test results revealed no significant improvement in LDL-C target achievement after intervention ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics.

Characteristic	Category	N (%)
Age (years)	≤ 40	1 (1.43)
	41–64	45 (64.29)
	≥ 65	24 (34.29)
Gender	Female	20 (28.57)
	Male	50 (71.43)
Marital status	Married	63 (90.00)
	Unmarried	1 (1.43)
	Widower	6 (8.57)
Educational level	Low	15 (21.43)
	Moderate	32 (45.71)
	High	23 (32.86)
Employment status	Employed	23 (32.86)
	Unemployed	47 (67.14)
Comorbidities		
	Hypertension	Yes
	No	16 (22.86)
Diabetes mellitus	Yes	34 (48.57)
	No	36 (51.43)
Heart failure	Yes	11 (15.71)
	No	59 (84.29)
Stroke	Yes	9 (12.86)
	No	61 (87.14)
Smoking history	Smoking	44 (62.86)
	Non-smoking	26 (37.14)
Duration of therapy	≤ 1 year	12 (17.14)
	> 1 year	58 (82.86)
Polypharmacy	Non-polypharmacy	13 (18.57)
	Polypharmacy	57 (81.43)
Caregiver	Accompanied	28 (40.00)
	Unaccompanied	42 (60.00)

Table 2. Medication adherence pre- and post-tailored intervention based on ARMS-SF.

Item	Question	N = 70									
		None of the time		Some of the time		Most of the time		All of the time		Mean ARMS score	
		Pre n(%)	Post n(%)	Pre n(%)	Post n(%)	Pre n(%)	post n(%)	pre n(%)	post n(%)	pre n(%)	post n(%)
Indicator: Medication refill adherence											
3	How often do you decide not to take your medicine?	69	70	1	0	0	0	0	0	1.01	1
		-98.57	-100	-1.43	0	0	0	0	0		
4	How often do you forget to get prescriptions refilled?	46	69	24	1	0	0	0	0	1.34	1.01
		-65.71	-98.57	-34.29	-1.43	0	0	0	0		
7	How frequently do you skip taking your medication when you feel that your condition has improved?	0	0	4	0	13	2	53	68	1.3	1.03
		0	0	-5.72	0	-18.57	-2.86	-75.71	-97.14		
Total mean ARMS score										3.65	3.04
Indicator: Medication intake adherence											
1	How often do you miss scheduled appointments?	6	67	51	3	13	0	0	0	2.1	1.04
		-8.57	-95.71	-72.86	-4.29	-18.57	0	0	0		
2	How often do you forget to take your medicine?	54	67	14	3	2	0	0	0	1.26	1.04
		-77.14	-95.71	-20	-4.29	-2.86	0	0	0		
5	How often do you run out of medicine?	62	68	8	2	0	0	0	0	1.1	1.03
		-88.57	-97.14	-11.43	-2.86	0	0	0	0		
6	How often do you skip a dose of your medicine before you go to visit the doctor?	69	70	1	0	0	0	0	0	1.01	1
		-98.57	-100	-1.43	0	0	0	0	0		
Total mean ARMS score										5.47	4.11

Table 3. Adherence percentage following the tailored intervention.

	Pre-intervention n (%)	Post-intervention n (%)	p-value*
Adherence to medication pre- and post-tailored intervention			
Adherence	0 (0.00)	63 (90)	<0.001

Discussion

Interpretation of findings and comparison with literature

This study represents the first Indonesian research evaluating the impact of a tailored intervention on LDL-C levels. Seventy volunteers were recruited, with their clinical characteristics and sociodemographic information outlined in Table 1. The predominant demographic of patients was male (71.43%), with the majority aged between 41 and 64 years (64.29%). These findings correspond with recent studies indicating the greatest prevalence of ASCVD in the 40–59 age demographic (AlQuaiz et al. 2021). Age, an immutable risk factor, correlates with a 2.4-fold and 3.7-fold elevation in cardiovascular risk at ages 50–60 and 60–70, respectively (Rezaianzadeh et al. 2023). The male predominance reflects how men exhibit a higher risk than women for developing ASCVD, which is further exacerbated by smoking (Gao et al. 2019).

A significant portion of the participants (45.71%) had attained a moderate education level, while the majority

(67.14%) were unemployed. This supports research connecting lower educational attainment to multiple cardiovascular risk factors, such as obesity, dyslipidemia, diabetes, hypertension, and detrimental lifestyles resulting from restricted access to health education and diminished awareness of related risks. Individuals with lower educational attainment exhibited difficulty in understanding the importance of adhering to treatment protocols and engaging in preventive practices, such as regular health monitoring. Consequently, these individuals were more likely to develop serious cardiovascular conditions, such as atherosclerosis, ischemic heart disease, and cerebrovascular accidents, even leading to early death. The inability to implement preventive measures owing to inadequate health literacy correlated with heightened morbidity and mortality rates (Khaing et al. 2017). The principal comorbidities comprised hypertension (77.14%), diabetes mellitus (48.57%), heart failure (15.71%), and stroke (12.86%). These results align with those presented by Pereira et al. (2022).

The McNemar test results demonstrated a substantial improvement in adherence post-intervention ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the tailored intervention could significantly enhance medication adherence. Our findings align with a Spanish study demonstrating that tailored intervention increased medication adherence from 0% to 56.4% (Oñatibia-Astibia et al. 2019). A similar study in Indonesia concerning patients with type 2 diabetes and hypertension observed

Table 4. LDL-C level reduction after tailored intervention.

Category	Difference in LDL reduction (mg/dL)	% LDL reduction	p-value
Pre-intervention LDL-C – Baseline LDL-C ^a	-17.77	15.06	<0.001
Post-intervention LDL-C – Baseline LDL-C ^b	-30.67	26.00	<0.001
Post-intervention LDL-C – Pre-intervention LDL-C ^a	-12.90	12.88	<0.001

^aSignificance using the Wilcoxon test.

^bSignificance using paired t-test.

Table 5. Relationship between adherence and LDL-C reduction post-tailored intervention.

	Adherence	Non-adherence	p-value*
Δ LDL = post LDL – pre LDL (mg/dL)	-14.48	13.71	0.019

*Significance using linear regression.

Table 6. LDL-C target achievement pre- and post-tailored intervention.

	Pre-intervention n (%)	Post-intervention n (%)	p-value*
LDL-C target achievement pre- and post-tailored intervention			
Achieved	0	2 (2.86)	0.50

*Significance using the McNemar test.

a significant increase in adherence from 0% to 68.42% (Alfian et al. 2021). Comparable results were observed in hypertensive patients, with adherence rates of 98.7% in the tailored intervention group compared to 59% in the non-tailored group (Esquivel Garzón et al. 2022). These findings suggest that non-tailored interventions often fail to address specific barriers to medication adherence in individuals.

The intervention group reduced their LDL-C levels by 10.00 mg/dL, from 113.3 mg/dL to 103.3 mg/dL, while the control group reduced their levels by 9.4 mg/dL, from 117.9 mg/dL to 108.5 mg/dL, according to a prior study by Choudhry et al. (2018). Our study's LDL-C reduction of 12.9 mg/dL was higher than that of previous studies.

A binary logistic regression analysis was performed to examine the association between achieving LDL-C targets and medication adherence. The findings indicated no significant correlation ($p > 0.05$), implying that adherence may not substantially affect LDL-C target attainment.

Although tailored interventions are demonstrated to be effective, their implementation, particularly in developing countries, poses challenges. Tailored interventions require multiple steps, such as identifying non-adherent patients, assessing specific barriers to adherence, and developing individualized strategies to overcome these barriers. This approach demands more effort and greater technical expertise than conventional interventions. However, a study reported that such interventions yield a positive return on investment and a cost per quality-adjusted life year (QALY) below widely accepted benchmarks for cardiovascular disease prevention (Jacob et al. 2022). Therefore, from a cost perspective, a tailored intervention may be cost-effective.

Possible reasons for limited target achievement

Aside from medication noncompliance, several factors may contribute to inadequate statin response. Familial hypercholesterolemia (FH) and secondary dyslipidemias are two prevalent lipid diseases that potentially cause statin hyporesponsiveness. Mutations in the gene that encodes low-density lipoprotein receptors (LDLRs) are the root cause of familial hypercholesterolemia (FH), a prevalent hereditary condition. People with an LDLR

mutation often do not respond well to statins, which is surprising because LDLR is crucial for the effectiveness of these drugs. Kim et al. (2020) discovered that the mutation's effect on LDLR function is variable. Uncommon etiologies encompass heterozygous mutations in the Apo-B gene that alter its LDLR-binding domain or heterozygous gain-of-function mutations in PCSK9 (Nordestgaard et al. 2013; Brandts and Ray 2021).

Several ailments correlate with a diminished statin response, including obesity, inflammatory diseases, nephrotic disease, cholestasis, and hypothyroidism. These conditions often result from underlying causes of dyslipidemia, which account for a third of all cases. This is typically a result of concurrent pharmacological treatments or acquired medical conditions (Yanai and Yoshida 2021). In some cases, researchers have found why these secondary dyslipidemias occasionally result in statin hyporesponsiveness. Individuals with hypothyroidism often have elevated levels of LDL-C and respond poorly to statins. This phenomenon is attributed to a decrease in hepatic LDLR due to a decrease in triiodothyronine levels, while triiodothyronine is essential for optimal gene expression via the receptor (Duntas 2002).

The efficacy of statins in improving lipid profiles is well-documented but varies among individuals due to genetic polymorphisms. The most common polymorphisms associated with atorvastatin are the SLCO1B, CYP7A1, and Apo-E genes. Research on the SLCO1B gene showed that patients who carry the 521CC genotype have had a smaller LDL-C reduction of 19.7% (Sivkov et al. 2021). The polymorphism of the Apo-E CC (rs7412) gene, specifically the $\epsilon 4$ phenotype, resulted in lower effectiveness in reducing LDL-C levels compared to the $\epsilon 2$ and $\epsilon 3$ phenotypes, which necessitated a higher dose intensification (Mega et al. 2009; Zhang et al. 2019; Asiimwe et al. 2024). Meanwhile, a study on Apo-E genotypes showed that the $\epsilon 4$ phenotype led to an LDL-C reduction of 23.05%, while $\epsilon 2$ and $\epsilon 3$ led to reductions of 29.41% and 27.25%, respectively (Zhang et al. 2019).

Identifying secondary causes and performing genetic testing could help predict patient responses to statins and optimize treatment plans. Examining the causes of statin hyporesponsiveness is a complex, multi-stage process, but ensuring patient adherence must be the priority. Tailored interventions should be recommended by pharmacists as an effective way to improve medication adherence.

This research tackles a significant clinical concern by utilizing a personalized intervention approach in a practical context in Indonesia. Nevertheless, these findings should be regarded with caution owing to the absence of a control group. Consequently, future randomized controlled trials are necessary to elucidate the causal relationship.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a tailored intervention administered by pharmacists significantly enhanced medication adherence and decreased LDL-C levels in patients on

high-intensity statins. Tailored interventions should be advised to enhance medication adherence prior to therapy intensification or polymorphism assessment. Future randomized controlled trials are necessary to establish a conclusive cause-and-effect relationship.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

This research was approved with an ethical certificate 1022/KEPK/VI/2024.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Airlangga University Hospital.

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Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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